

Optimization of microwave irradiated synthesis parameters of eggshell derived hydroxyapatite at lab scale

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Abstract

Hydroxyapatite (HAp) is a calcium phosphate bioceramic material which forms major inorganic component of human hard tissues (bones and teeth). It is widely used as bone substitutematerial in orthopedic and dental applications. Also it has an excellent biocompatibility, osteoinductivity and ability to promote osteoblast functions. There are several reports on the synthesis of HAp from biogenic biowaste minerals such as marine shells, snail shells, mussel shells and eggshellsusing direct and indirect conversion methods. The microwave synthesis of ceramics has several advantages including shorter synthesis time, fast reaction, easy reproducibility, narrow particle size distribution, etc. Phase pure HAp powder was synthesized by lab scale microwave irradiation method using eggshell as the calcium precursor. The optimizationof synthesis parameters such as pH, microwave power, volume and EDTA concentrationswill be discussed.

Keywords: Hydroxyapatite, Eggshell and Microwave irradiation